

Data Table 3. Genetic distance vs. physical distance for parental, hybrid and mutant hybrid strains. Chromosome sizes are based on S288C (SGD). Information for *S. cerevisiae* is from the SGD and for the hybrid wild type is from Kao et al. (2010) based on 58 random spores. Information for the hybrid mutant is based on 84 tetrads.

Chromosome	Size (kbp)	<i>S. cerevisiae</i> (S288c)	Hybrid (pCLB2-SGS1 pCLB2-MSH2)			Hybrid (wild type)		
		cmM/kbp	# of CO	cM	cmM/kbp	# of CO	cM	cmM/kbp
I	240	0.45	92	54.76	0.23	4	6.9	0.029
II	820	0.3	179	106.55	0.13	11	18.97	0.023
III	320	0.48	118	70.24	0.22	1	1.72	0.0054
IV	1530	0.31	348	207.14	0.14	22.5	38.79	0.025
V	580	0.35	152	90.48	0.16	12	20.69	0.036
VI	280	0.48	62	36.9	0.13	5	8.62	0.031
VII	1100	0.37	255	151.79	0.14	12	20.69	0.019
VIII	570	0.3	173	102.98	0.18	5	8.62	0.015
IX	440	0.45	123	73.21	0.17	5	8.62	0.02
X	750	0.3	210	125	0.17	10	17.24	0.023
XI	670	0.38	175	104.17	0.16	7.5	12.93	0.019
XII	1080	0.36	289	172.024	0.16	13.5	23.28	0.022
XIII	930	0.34	235	139.88	0.15	14.5	25	0.027
XIV	790	0.37	175	104.17	0.13	9.5	16.38	0.021
XV	1100	0.33	292	173.81	0.16	12.5	21.55	0.02
XVI	950	0.29	304	180.95	0.19	9.5	16.38	0.017